

SURKHANDARYA REGION SOIL AND CLIMATIC CONDITIONS: EFFECTIVE OPPORTUNITIES FOR PEANUT CULTIVATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18065526>

Abstract. *Today, ensuring food safety for the rapidly growing global population is considered a pressing issue. This article presents information about measures being implemented in our country and the European Union regarding this urgent matter.*

Keywords: *population, harmful organisms, food safety, plant protection, pesticides, residual contamination level, environmentally friendly products, biological methods, bioproducts, etc.*

Introduction

According to Resolution PQ-136 issued on 08.04.2025 by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “On additional measures to increase the export potential of agricultural products and develop the processing chain,” special attention is given to increasing the volume of high-quality export-oriented agricultural products grown and packaged in our country. Due to its economic importance, peanuts are considered an effective export crop that meets international standards. Today, peanuts grown in Uzbekistan are exported to Austria, Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Belarus, Georgia, Iraq, Iran, Kazakhstan, China, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Mongolia, the UAE, Pakistan, Poland, Russia, Serbia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and other countries.

On June 16 of this year, during the national video conference chaired by the President, it was emphasized—using Surkhandarya region as an example—that, considering soil and climate conditions, it is possible to harvest crops three times a year. The President highlighted that sowing secondary crops on land freed after grain harvest is practical and beneficial.

It is important to note that Surkhandarya, the southernmost region of the country, has favorable conditions for year-round agricultural land use, with sufficient land and water resources. Based on its soil and climate characteristics, peanuts are one of the most suitable and productive crops for repeated planting. Selecting high-yielding, stable varieties adapted to the geographic region is an essential prerequisite for this purpose. Supplying the growing world population with safe and environmentally clean food products has become one of the most pressing issues. In Uzbekistan, the Law “On Food Safety” (O‘RQ-1023) consisting of 25 articles was adopted on 03.02.2025. The purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of food safety.

In recent years, wide-ranging economic, organizational, and legal reforms have been implemented to develop the agricultural sector. This includes Resolution PQ-4118 (16.01.2019) “On additional measures for the development of the oil and fat industry and introduction of market mechanisms in its management,” and the Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 438 (14.07.2025) “On additional measures for developing the production of oilseed crops.”

Although these resolutions aim to expand production volumes and diversify products within the oil and fat industry, problems such as the lack of a unified management system, ineffective product quality control, insufficient adoption of advanced technologies, limited investment, and restricted raw material base continue to hinder sector development. As a result, the production capacity utilization rate of enterprises remains below 50%. These resolutions outline clear tasks aimed at ensuring food security, increasing export potential through competitive products, and ensuring year-round stable supplies of agricultural products.

Ensuring the availability of affordable, high-quality vegetable oil for the population requires selecting early-ripening, high-yielding, stress-resistant, export-oriented varieties appropriate for different ecological regions. Establishing seed production and resource-efficient cultivation technologies is one of today's urgent issues. For this reason, the Ministry of Agriculture of Uzbekistan plans to introduce peanut cultivation on post-grain fields in Surkhandarya, not only to improve the region's economy but also to restore natural soil fertility. Scientific evidence shows that legumes are among the most effective crops for restoring soil fertility. Among them, peanuts stand out due to their high economic value. For this reason, peanuts are included in crop rotation systems in highly developed agricultural countries, including the USA.

Currently, peanuts are grown in 109 countries, with 82% of global production concentrated in only 10 countries. As of January 2023, total global peanut production was 50.2 million tons. The largest producers are China—18.3 million tons (36%), India—6.6 million tons (13%), Nigeria—4.5 million tons (9%), the USA and Sudan—2.5 million tons each (5%), Senegal and Myanmar—1.7 million tons (3%), Argentina—1.3 million tons (2%), Guinea and Tanzania—1.2 and 1.1 million tons (2%). Despite being the world's largest peanut exporter in recent years, China actively seeks to purchase peanuts grown in Uzbekistan due to their compliance with global standards and superior ecological purity. According to the US Department of Agriculture, peanuts rank fifth among the world's major oilseed crops.

Peanut kernels contain 48–54% easily digestible oil and up to 27% protein. In terms of taste, peanut oil is comparable to olive oil. It is widely used for preparing salads, canned foods, and margarine. In confectionery alone, more than 60 products—including edible oil, chocolates, cookies, halva, candies, and ice cream—use peanuts as a primary ingredient. Compared to other legumes and oilseed crops, peanuts are highly profitable and virtually waste-free. Peanut vines serve as nutritious forage for livestock, containing up to 11% protein, essential vitamins, and minerals—similar to clover and alfalfa. On average, 280–320 bales of hay can be obtained per hectare. Peanut meal, containing 48% protein and 8% residual oil, is a valuable feed for livestock and poultry (Podgorniy, 1976).

Peanuts are highly effective for improving soil fertility. Their root nodules contain nitrogen-fixing bacteria capable of enriching the soil with 60–70 kg of nitrogen per hectare, and their organic residues significantly increase soil humus content (Yormatova, 2008).

Methodology

Research was conducted on the valuable biological and agronomic characteristics of the peanut varieties “Salomat,” “Mumtoz,” “Qibray-4,” and “Lider.” The methodologies used were based on guidelines from the All-Union Institute of Plant Industry (VIR, 1986), the Institute of Plant Genetic Resources (Tashkent, 2010), and methods for monitoring pests and diseases (VIZR 1985; Dement'eva, 1985; Khojaev, 2004). Yield data were processed statistically according to B.A. Dospexov (1985).

Results

Research results show that introducing high-yield peanut varieties adapted to the Surkhandarya climate increases yields by 1.5–1.8 times and net income by 55–60%. This contributes to regional agricultural development, investor attraction, job creation, and export potential growth.

Currently, the local variety “Tashkent-112” is commonly grown in post-grain fields in Surkhandarya. Its average yield is 12–16 t/ha, with a seed weight of 300–350 grams per 1,000 seeds. However, it does not meet international standards in terms of shape and color. Created in 1952 by researchers of the VIR Middle Asian branch, its yield and quality have declined due to the lack of long-term seed renewal. After independence, scientists developed four high-yielding, large-seeded (650–1100 g per 1,000 seeds), export-

oriented varieties—“Qibray-4” (2002), “Mumtoz” (2006), “Salomat” (2006), and “Lider” (2017).

Description of peanut varieties Intended for testing under the soil and climatic conditions of Surkhandarya region.

“Mumtaz” Peanut Variety

The “Mumtaz” peanut variety belongs to the *Hypogaea* (Virginia or Runner) variety group. It is a mid-early maturing variety with a vegetation period of 140–150 days and high productivity (40–45 centners per hectare). The seeds are medium-sized, dark red in color, with a 1000-seed weight of 650–700 g.

This variety is suitable for consumption as dried nuts, for confectionery products, and for oil. Single-plant type production. The seeds are uniform, oval-round in shape, and suitable for export. The variety is drought-resistant, and the pods mature simultaneously. The nuts are clustered around the base of the plant. It meets international market standards, and the oil content of the seeds is 50–51%. In terms of seed size and yield, it is twice as productive as the local “Tashkent-112” variety.

The plant height is 30–35 cm. On average, 280–290 stems are harvested per hectare.

“Qibray-4” Peanut Variety

The “Qibray-4” variety belongs to the *Hypogaea* group. It is a mid-early maturing variety with a vegetation period of 150 days and high productivity (45 centners per hectare). The seeds are large, pink-colored, with a 1000-seed weight of 900 g.

It is suitable for consumption as dried nuts and for the production of confectionery products. The variety is competitive and developed for export purposes. The plant height is 45–50 cm. The nuts are clustered at the base of the plant. It meets international market standards, and the oil content of the seeds is 46–48%. Compared to the local “Tashkent-112” variety, it is twice as productive in yield and two and a half times larger in seed size. On average, 300–310 stems are harvested per hectare. One plant forms an average of 50–80 nuts. The seeds are uniform, oval-elongated, and suitable for export.

“Lider” Peanut Variety

The “Lider” variety belongs to the *Hypogaea* (Virginia or Runner) group. It is a mid-early maturing variety with a vegetation period of 145–150 days and very high productivity (50–65 centners per hectare). The seeds are large, red in color, oval-shaped, with a 1000-seed weight of 1000–1050 g.

This variety was developed through hybridization of Indian and U.S. samples and long-term selection (1999–2015), and it was included in the State Register in 2017. It is considered a universal variety, competitive, and intended for export.

The nuts are clustered at the base of the plant. It meets international market standards, and the oil content of the seeds is 49–50%. In terms of yield, it is twice as productive as the local “Tashkent-112” variety, and in terms of seed size, it is three times larger. On average, 300–310 stems are harvested per hectare. One plant forms an average of 70–90 nuts. The seeds are uniform, oval-shaped, and suitable for export.

It meets international market standards, and the oil content of the seeds составляет 49–50%. In terms of yield, it is twice as productive as the local “Tashkent-112” variety, while in terms of seed size, it is three times larger. On average, 300–310 stems are harvested per hectare. One plant forms an average of 70–90 pods. The seeds are uniform, oval-shaped, and suitable for export.

Local “Tashkent-112” Peanut Variety

The local “Tashkent-112” variety belongs to the Valencia group. It is a mid-early maturing variety with a vegetation period of 120–130 days and moderate productivity (20–25 centners per hectare).

The seeds are small, red in color, with a 1000-seed weight of 300–350 g, and have various shapes.

This variety is suitable for consumption as dried nuts and for oil production. It is not suitable for export and is sold only on the domestic market.

Double-plant type

The nuts are clustered at the base of the plant, and the oil content of the seeds is 49–50%. The main stem length is 50–60 cm. On average, 300–350 stems are harvested per hectare. One plant forms an average of 20–30 nuts.

These varieties will be tested and cultivation technologies optimized for Surkhandarya’s climate. Field seminars will be organized for farmers and exporters, and primary and certified seed production systems will be established.

Due to increasing global population and demand for food, the cultivation areas of legumes and oilseeds continue to expand. Peanuts, rich in oil and protein, are used in canned goods,

confectionery, margarine, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals. Peanut meal and cake are important livestock feed. Forecasts for 2022 predicted 34,189 hectares of peanut fields in Uzbekistan (7,402 ha primary crops, 26,787 ha secondary crops), with an expected yield of 86,434 tons. However, actual yields did not meet expectations.

In Surkhandarya, only 209.7 hectares are currently used for peanut cultivation, although at least 1,000 hectares have high potential. Research will identify high-yielding, export-oriented varieties and improve cultivation technologies. An integrated pest and disease management system will be developed. As a result, yields and net profits can increase 1.5–2 times.

Expanding peanut cultivation areas will increase employment, support small processing enterprises, and boost regional export potential. Scientific and practical guidelines will be developed for producing high-quality peanut yields.

At present, 1 kg of unshelled peanut seeds costs around 15,000 soums. With an average yield of 4 tons per hectare, farmers can earn 60 million soums from kernels and 9 million soums from hay. Additionally, peanut residues enrich the soil with nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and other elements.

Peanuts are affected by more than 90 diseases (root rots, powdery mildew, rust, bacterial and viral infections) and pests (wireworms, grubs, weevils, spider mites, and others). Integrated pest management is recommended to control these harmful organisms.

Conclusion

Expanding peanut cultivation as both a primary and secondary crop and ensuring scientifically based, efficient use of this plant are key factors in ensuring food security, supporting healthy lifestyles, creating employment, and developing environmentally stable agriculture. Therefore, researching, cultivating, and processing peanuts using modern agrotechnologies is an important and promising economic strategy. Practical research projects in this direction are planned.

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